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D5.4

Urban climate data platform

PUCS has received funding
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Deliverable 5.4

Urban climate data platform

Related Work Package:
 Deliverable lead:
 Author(s):
 Contact for queries
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 Instrument:
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 Website:
 Abstract

WP5
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To facilitate the storage and distribution of the urban primary climate data that are generated in this project (see deliverables 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3), a distribution platform is set up by VITO. This platform integrates all the raw urban climate data and provides functionalities to select and export the information needed by the service providers. The data are publicly available and the platform will be sustained after the end of the project.

Dissemination level of the document

X	PU	Public
	PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
	RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the European Commission Services)
	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the European Commission Services)

Versioning and Contribution History

Version	Date	Modified by	Modification reasons
v.02			
v.03			
v.04			
v.05			

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1. Introduction

This document is developed as part of the PUCS (Pan-European Climate Service) project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, under the Grant Agreement number 730004¹. For marketing purposes, the project name is changed to 'Climate-fit.city' for internal useage and communication to end-users and stakeholders. The "Urban climate data platform" represents **Deliverable 5.4** of Work Package 5 (WP5) – Urban climate data platform. The objective of PUCS is to establish services that translate the best available scientific urban climate data into relevant information for public and private end-users operating in cities. This will be achieved by demonstrating the benefits of urban climate information to end-users, considering the sectors of health, energy, emergency planning, urban planning, mobility, and cultural heritage.

Previous deliverables of this work package focussed on the process of data needs collection (Deliverable 5.1) and the production process of the required urban climate data (Deliverables 5.2 and 5.3). The present deliverable confirms that all these data can now be visualised and downloaded from an online web platform.

¹ SC5-01-2016-2017: Exploiting the added value of climate services – a) Demonstration of climate services (2016 – Innovation Action – IA)

2. Urban climate data platform

Based on the specific data needs of the service providers for the 6 demonstration and replication cases, VITO and KU Leuven have produced the required primary urban climate data. To facilitate the storage and distribution of these data, a distribution platform is set up by VITO. This platform provides functionalities to select and export the information needed by its users:

- Data selection: catalogue to select the city and/or the urban area of interest; the information needed including the climate scenario and time horizon.

- Data visualisation: to allow a quick scan visualisation of the data/information of interest.

- Data export: download the information needed in the format (raw data in Netcdf format and GIS (GeoTIFF) overview maps) specified by the service providers.

The screenshot shows the 'Urban Climate Data Portal' interface. The main heading is 'Download Urban Climate Data'. The form includes the following fields and options:

- Select a city:** A dropdown menu with 'Barcelona, Spain' selected.
- Data type:** Radio buttons for 'Map (.tiff)' and 'Data (.netcdf)'. 'Data (.netcdf)' is selected.
- Variable:** A text input field containing 'Air temperature'.
- Data scope:** Radio buttons for 'Historical data' and 'Future data'. 'Future data' is selected.
- Period:** A dropdown menu with '2085' selected.
- Climate scenario:** Radio buttons for 'RCP 4.5' and 'RCP 8.5'. 'RCP 8.5' is selected.

A red 'DOWNLOAD' button with a download icon is located at the bottom of the form.

A professional functional analyst was involved in this task to validate and test the aspects of the distribution platform with the service providers before the implementation. During two projects meetings, mock-ups of the data portal were presented to the service providers and feedback was given.

The data on the portal will be publicly available following the Open Data Policy. After the end of the project, the platform will be sustained. VITO and KU Leuven will continue to use the platform in their activities following up on the Climate-fit.city project and future new service providers.

The platform can be accessed through this link : <https://dataplatfomr.climate-fit.city/>

Figure 1: Home page of the urban climate data platform

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the benefits of
climate services

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